

helios: Design and prototypical implementation of a C++ game framework

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Abstract

We present *helios*, a prototype game framework developed in C++ for creating a *Geometry Wars* clone. We outline the framework’s overall structure and describe the functionalities of its existing modules. Furthermore, we justify key architectural and design decisions and discuss the challenges encountered during development. Finally, we provide an outlook on the areas where major changes and refinements are expected in the subsequent stages of development.

1 Introduction

We are developing a *Geometry Wars*¹ clone in C++. Our implementation is partly based on the widely used game engine architecture described by Gregory [23], although we deliberately reduce the number of abstraction layers and omit systems such as tooling, sound, and scripting (cf. [23, Figure 1.16, 39]). The resulting technical foundation therefore resembles a framework rather than a full-fledged engine. The actual game - as a *black box* [27] - is designed to use this framework’s interfaces to access hardware and other subsystems.

The following sections present the architecture of the framework referred to as **helios**². We explicitly take into account its prototypical development status: the software is being

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Geometry Wars is a trademark of Activision Publishing, Inc.; this work is not affiliated with Activision. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17564822.

¹See [54]

²Helios, who “looks around sharply with shining eyes“ (*Homers Ilias*, Gesang 14, own translation), is the sun god in Greek mythology.

Figure 1: The *helios* project logo. (Source: own representation)

created as part of an agile *Tracer Bullet Development* process [49, pp. 50-55], allowing the entire system to be adapted on short notice if necessary. Requirements for the architecture are derived accordingly. Project data and objectives are presented separately in Section 2.

We also address the problems and challenges encountered during the implementation so far. These arise, among other things, from the fact that the software product - developed within a comparatively short time frame - is to be evaluated not only on the basis of objective measures (such as the number of defects, software design decisions, or the degree of object coupling) but also on the basis of subjective criteria [3, p. 385]. Although there are no plans to classify the finished product according to usability quality characteristics such as those defined in ISO/IEC 9126³, the result should not only be technically robust but also enjoyable to use. In the following, we summarize this user experience in the more informal but established term *game feel* [46], widely used in game development.

2 Project Data and Goals

The goal of this project is to create a stable prototype of the twin-stick shooter⁴ *Geometry Wars* (see Figure 2) using the C++23 programming language and the OpenGL API [24].

The following features were agreed upon for implementation:

- Playable level (2D grid)

³Usability quality according to ISO/IEC 9126 in [3, p. 466]; see also studies and investigations in [1], [5].

⁴For genre classification, see also [52].

Figure 2: *Geometry Wars* first appeared in 2003 as an Easter egg in the game *Project Gotham Racing 2* (Microsoft Game Studios). Due to its great popularity, several sequels were released, most recently in 2016 with *Geometry Wars 3: Dimensions Evolved* (Activision). (Source: Activision Publishing, Inc.)

- Time attack mode with a duration of 3 minutes
- High score system
- Controller support
- Stable frame rate of at least 60 FPS with simultaneous display of over one hundred enemies and objects
- Three enemy types with simple AI (“spawn and chase“)
- Enhancement of the game feel through graphical effects
- Compilable and executable under Windows 11

While some criteria are specifically measurable (e.g., frame rate), other requirements are deliberately vague (e.g., game feel) and underscore the exploratory nature of the project. Formal requirements engineering is therefore not part of this work, especially since the original game on which the implementation is based also serves as a reference and benchmark.

The learning process itself is considered a key objective of this project; no formal metrics are used for its evaluation. Instead, the experiences and results obtained are documented in writing, and the present report will serve as a critical reflection of them at the end of the project.

Against this background, the approach can be regarded as a form of dynamic requirements engineering “with significantly greater degrees of freedom“ [35, p. 60] (own translation). The aforementioned *Tracer Bullet Development* process, which primarily provides a platform for integration, corresponds to the prototype referred to by Pflug et al. as a “living lab“, which is further developed using agile methods (*ibid.*, p. 61), allowing for the contribution of original creative ideas.⁵

2.1 Schedule

The schedule and associated milestones are presented in Table 1. The timeline serves as a guideline for implementation; the sequential listing does not imply a waterfall model. Since the game concept to be implemented is already defined, there is no need for an exploratory prototype phase. The current stage of development can be classified as the *hard-architecture design* phase, following Rollings and Morris [39, pp. 628-630].

The project is published under the MIT license on GitHub, with both the source code and the issue tracker publicly accessible [44].

⁵In [29], Kasurinen et al. explore whether requirements management, which is rooted in engineering, has a place in game development, a field strongly influenced by creative processes. They show that some requirements are consciously derived through *user testing*. Accordingly, games user research has become an important branch of the games industry that helps developers understand and improve the player experience ([57, p. 26]). Further discussions regarding software engineering in game development can be found in Kanode and Haddad [28].

Milestone	Date	Content
milestone_1	2025-10-20	Provision of the application layer, including implementation of the event system, the input manager, and connection to the low-level API subsystem.
milestone_2	2025-11-17	Provision of the rendering engine; initial design of the playing field, including display of the player's ship.
milestone_3	2025-12-22	Implementation of physics and player input for ship control; fire mechanics.
milestone_4	2026-01-19	Implementation of the core game rules and mechanics; playable prototype.
milestone_5	2026-02-09	Provision of the prototype; fine-tuning.
milestone_6	2026-03-16	Submission of documentation and presentation of the project.

Table 1: Planned milestones for the implementation of the *Geometry Wars* clone. At the time of publication of this document, the first milestone has been completed: *helios* already provides simple window management, rudimentary input processing, a logging system, and a functional rendering layer with a connection to the OpenGL API.

3 Project Structure

We present the structure of the project and the associated toolchain. We also briefly introduce the contents of the individual directories.

The top level of the *helios* directory structure provides access to tests, executable sample programs, benchmarks, documentation, and source files. The chosen structure follows the conventions for C++ projects defined by the *Pitchfork* project [36]. The directory names are self-explanatory and are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Project directory of *helios* (excerpt).

The project comprises several build stages to compile the source files and generate the tests and example programs. For automation, we use CMake [30], which also allows us to perform simple dependency management. The third-party libraries (TPLs) required for development (including `glfw` [17] and `glad` [26]) can thus be fetched directly from external sources, statically compiled, and integrated (see Listing 1). This approach enables us to automate the project’s preconfiguration and avoid manual (and often error-prone [11]) integration of TPLs.

```
1 ...
2 FetchContent_Declare(glfw
3     GIT_REPOSITORY [url]
4     GIT_TAG        3.4
5 )
6
7 FetchContent_Declare(glad
8     GIT_REPOSITORY [url]
9     GIT_TAG        v2.0.8
10    SOURCE_SUBDIR  cmake
11 )
12
13 FetchContent_MakeAvailable(glfw glad)
14
15 # GLAD v2: Core GL 4.6
16 glad_add_library(
17     glad_gl_core_46 STATIC REPRODUCIBLE LOADER API
18     gl:core=4.6
19 )
20 ...
```

Listing 1: Excerpt from `helios`’ `CMakeLists.txt`. This section declares and fetches GLFW v3.4 and GLAD v2.0.8 via `FetchContent` from the respective GitHub repositories (URLs omitted for clarity). Subsequently, a GLAD loader for OpenGL 4.6 is created as a static library.

3.1 Directory Contents

In the following, we present the main directories in alphabetical order and briefly discuss their contents.

`/benchmarks`

For benchmarking individual functions, *helios* uses *Google Benchmark* [20]. Currently, there are benchmarks for mathematical types and functions. We use these to compare our implementations with those of `glm` [18], which serves as a reference. This allows us to identify potential bottlenecks in the *Game Loop* at an early stage, for example in operations involving affine transformation matrices. Further benchmarks - measuring

Benchmark	Time	CPU	Iterations
BM_mat4Constructor/real_time	5.81 ns	5.85 ns	106,874,145
BM_mat4Multiply/real_time	175 ns	168 ns	3,896,895

Table 2: Sample output of benchmark results based on our custom `mat4` implementation.

the performance of selected functions in the *Rendering Pipeline* or *Application Stage* [23, p. 687] (e.g., during *Culling*) - are planned.

No evaluation of alternative benchmarking frameworks was conducted; the choice was based on popularity and community recommendations.

/docs

In addition to formal documentation⁶, this directory contains API documentation generated from the source files using `doxygen` [51]. A key advantage of `doxygen` is its ability to export to multiple formats. This allows us to generate HTML or XML documentation and integrate it into the *helios* project website [45] via a dedicated build step.

A formal evaluation of documentation tools was not performed. The selection was guided by ease of integration and widespread adoption. We also consider the extensive range of output formats (including PDF and Markdown) beneficial for maintaining project documentation.

/tests

For unit testing, *helios* employs *Google Test* [21]. To increase development speed, especially during the early and potentially unstable project phase, we initially decided against pursuing high test coverage. Current tests therefore focus on mathematical functions - for instance, validating transformations within the scene graph. *helios* uses `glm` as a test oracle [6, pp. 917-919] for comparison purposes.⁷

As with benchmarking, no formal evaluation of unit testing frameworks was conducted. The decision was based on popularity and recommendations.

/examples

This directory contains example programs that demonstrate the individual functionalities of the framework. During development, these programs help define functionalities in a *top-down approach* and refine them iteratively [56]. This approach allows us to focus on the required interfaces of individual subsystems without getting lost in implementation details that can be added in later iterations.

⁶Such as the \LaTeX source code of this document.

⁷Alternatively, `glm` can be regarded as a *baseline* against which *helios* functions (as a *delta version*) are compared in regression tests. We acknowledge that any errors in `glm` would propagate to *helios*; however, given the maturity of the *glm* project, this risk is considered minimal.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the `simple_cube_rendering` demo, used in a top-down approach to incrementally implement the functionality defined in the first milestone. (Source: own recording)

`/include`, `/src`

With C++23, *helios* implements its classes and functions entirely through Module Interface and Implementation Units [43, pp. 211-213]. These are stored in `/include` and `/src`, respectively. Modules not divided into Interface and Implementation Units reside exclusively in `/include` as “header-only” components. These include classes such as `helios::math::vec3`, which represents a three-dimensional vector type whose functions are predominantly declared as `constexpr`⁸. The directories are further subdivided into `ext` and `helios`:

- `ext` contains platform-specific implementations of interfaces contractually defined by the *helios* framework (hardware-related window and application abstractions, as well as rendering pipeline specifics).
- `helios` contains the actual framework code.

⁸The `constexpr` keyword allows expressions to be evaluated at compile time, requiring their complete definition at translation time [22, p. 330].

4 Architecture

In the following, we describe the architecture of *helios*, which is currently designed as shown in Figure 5: *helios* acts as an intermediary layer between the game as a real-time data model [23, p. 525] and the technical infrastructure. The framework visualizes the game state and transmits input data to the game as control commands.

Figure 5: Division of the architecture of the *helios* framework into *hard* and *soft architecture* according to Rollings and Morris [39, p. 612]. The ball-and-socket notation illustrates that *helios* provides interfaces that can be used by any game. (Source: own representation)

Figure 6 shows a more detailed view of the modules and selected components. The directory structure of *helios* mirrors the structure of its core functionalities. In the sense of *Evans*, this is crucial for high cohesion: the directory names communicate the functionalities they contain [10, pp. 180–181]. Within the modules, there is a further subdivision into layers (such as `controller`), following a “package-by-feature and -by-layer“ design approach.

app: Application layer

The central control unit of the application or game is the `Application` class, which provides an event system, input processing, and window management, and initializes the rendering backend represented by `RenderDevice`. *helios* also supports the dynamic addition of application controllers [13, pp. 379–382] to define isolated, event-based control logic, such as behavior during a window resize.⁹

⁹The application controllers were originally introduced to abstract “framebuffer resize“ events from the rendering backend.

Figure 6: Structure of the *helios* framework and relationships between selected components. The modules follow a “by-feature, by-layer“ concept in which features are internally divided into functional layers. (Source: own representation)

input: Input processing

The `InputManager` orchestrates input processing. It is managed exclusively by the application and bound to the active window. A specialized `InputAdapter` abstracts the input events provided by third-party libraries (TPLs) and translates them for the `InputManager`. At the beginning of each game loop, active input events are polled via `InputManager::poll()`. Events can be queried through convenience methods such as `InputManager::isKeyPressed()`.

event: Event processing

Events are written to an `EventQueue` (“*post*“) via the `EventManager`. Interested observers can register callbacks with the `EventManager` using `subscribe()` [16, pp. 293-303]. The method `EventManager::dispatchAll()` then notifies all registered observers of existing events.

window: Window management

The `Window` class provides interfaces for controlling the application window, handling window events, and triggering buffer swapping operations.

math: Mathematical types and operations

This module provides trigonometric functions and data types rooted in linear algebra, such as vectors and matrices, within the namespace `helios::math`. It also supports operations for linear and affine transformations, thereby implementing the coordinate space conversions commonly used in 3D computer graphics.¹⁰

Model \rightarrow World \rightarrow View \rightarrow Projection

The interfaces follow the method signatures of popular libraries such as the aforementioned `glm`.

scene: Scene graph

The scene graph `helios::scene::Scene` follows established designs in the literature.¹¹ `Scene` has an implicit root node that can contain any number of child nodes. Each `SceneNode` holds a `Transform` object describing the model transformation within its local coordinate system. `SceneNodes` can be “renderable“, i.e., configured with a `Renderable`, or they may represent other entities such as a `Camera` (`helios::scene::Camera`).¹² Nodes with a `Renderable` are considered during the *culling* process. The culling algorithm is defined abstractly in the pure virtual class `FrustumCullingStrategy`; concrete implementations are passed to the `Scene` upon instantiation. During the application stage [23, p. 687], *helios* generates a `Snapshot` from a scene and camera, using the configured culling strategy to collect all `SceneNodes` within the camera’s visible area. A single `Snapshot` forms the basis for a `RenderPass`, which holds the necessary `RenderCommands` for the rendering process. Listing 2 shows the sequence of a simple game loop.

```
1 while (!win->shouldClose()) {
2     app->eventManager().dispatchAll();
3
4     inputManager.poll(0.0f);
5
6     if (inputManager.isKeyPressed(Key::ESC)) {
7         win->setShouldClose(true);
8     }
9
10    snapshot = scene->createSnapshot(*camera);
11    renderPass = factory.buildRenderPass(snapshot);
12
13    app->renderingDevice().render(renderPass);
14
15    win->swapBuffers();
```

¹⁰After projection, the coordinates reside in so-called clip space. Typically, the rendering backend performs perspective division to convert these coordinates into normalized device coordinates (NDC) relevant for the rasterizer [2, p. 18].

¹¹See, among others, [41] and [23].

¹²In this context, other node types typically include (freely positionable) `LightNodes`, i.e., light sources.

Listing 2: Implementation of a simple game loop in *helios*. A `Snapshot` is created from the scene and serves as the basis for the `RenderPass`.

rendering: Render pipeline

The rendering system of *helios* is divided into several modules, including `shader` for GLSL¹³-related code and `model` for abstractions of material and mesh data. `Renderables` represent renderable objects, encapsulating all information necessary for the rendering process. They are modeled as aggregations, consisting of configurable `Material` and `Mesh` instances, which in turn share `MaterialData` and `MeshData` objects for efficient reuse [2, p. 126].

The information required for a `RenderPass` is collected as `RenderCommand` objects in a `RenderQueue`, which are processed by the `RenderDevice`: Each `RenderCommand` references the geometry to be rendered (`Mesh`), the `Shader` to be used, and data structures containing `Uniform` variables (e.g., transformation matrices). The `RenderDevice` processes a `RenderPass` via the template methods `preRender()`, `doRender()`, and `postRender()`.

util: Utility classes

The `helios::util` module contains non-domain-specific code, such as the `LogManager` for logging and a `Guid` implementation for assigning globally unique identifiers to objects.

5 Discussion of Implementation

In [34], Petrillo et al. describe several causes of *feature creep* in game development. These include developing proprietary solutions instead of using existing libraries, as well as adding ostensibly “attractive“ features that - per the YAGNI¹⁴ maxim - do not provide added value for the actual project goal. As the authors point out, this puts game development on a par with “ordinary“ software development, for example in the context of contract work. If the project also involves a technically unfamiliar domain that must be implemented within a tight timeframe, a sense of proportion and discipline are essential when adding functionality. With *helios*, we therefore pursue a top-down approach to enable rapid prototyping and, following the framework concept, to advance the step-by-step development and integration of the *Geometry Wars* clone. In this context, we regard the SOLID¹⁵ principles [32] as an indispensable basis for agile software development, as they are closely related to “clean software design“ and have already proven valuable in the development process to date.¹⁶

¹³*OpenGL Shading Language*

¹⁴*You Aren't Gonna Need It* [40].

¹⁵Single Responsibility Principle, Open-Closed Principle, Liskov Substitution Principle, Interface Segregation Principle, Dependency Inversion Principle.

¹⁶See Cabral et al. [8], who examine the applicability of SOLID in a machine-learning context - an environment characterized by “iterative experimentation with data, models, and algorithms“ (*ibid*).

To avoid the emergence of an unstructured, hard-to-maintain architecture (*Big Ball of Mud* [12]), we rely on a clear separation of responsibilities, reflected in the project’s feature layers. To reduce coupling between components - and thus improve maintainability and testability - we use *Dependency Injection* [42], primarily via *Constructor Injection* [14]. Since no dedicated DI container is used in the current implementation, the management of dependencies (*wiring*) in the source code results in some boilerplate, which is largely reduced by moving creation logic into static factory classes. This particularly benefits the example programs during development, which also serve as test drivers. In other subsystems, factory methods support the encapsulation of object creation within those entities that are also assigned technical responsibility in terms of domain logic [10, pp. 139-141]. In this way, the architecture of *helios* remains coherent, and dependencies between layers are kept to the necessary minimum.

Dealing with modern language features of a proven but also “traditional“ language such as C++ - notably the module system and smart pointers - has been challenging. We find ourselves balancing established C++ idioms [53] and proven concepts against a development environment largely shaped by experience with simpler high-level languages such as Java. Especially at the beginning of the project, the project structure and namespace identifiers were therefore repeatedly adjusted (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Code-frequency graph for the *helios* repository. Changes to the project structure in the early phase are reflected in the nearly symmetrical distribution of added (green) and removed (red) code. (Source: GitHub)

To express clear ownership in object management, we avoid raw pointers in many places.

They argue that applying the principles can contribute significantly to code comprehensibility.

Instead, we use the standard library types `unique_ptr`, `shared_ptr`, and `weak_ptr`, which manage ownership semantics exclusively (via *move*) or jointly (via reference counting). To what extent the additional CPU instructions resulting from this have a measurable impact on efficiency when building and processing the rendering pipeline remains to be evaluated if necessary.¹⁷

We see potential for optimization here, but in the early development phase we have consciously opted for stability and clear semantics. Later refactorings in favor of higher efficiency¹⁸ are acceptable, particularly since such measures only make sense once the domain has been sufficiently explored, both technically and from a subject-matter perspective.¹⁹

The choice of data structures and programming paradigms should also be mentioned: Our object relationships are currently very expressive (`Snapshot`, `Renderable`, `Material`, `Shader`, etc.), and we have so far avoided excessively deep inheritance hierarchies. The decision to use `std::vector` as the primary data container can negatively impact the rendering pipeline if the render queue must be rebuilt after a scene update and additional memory needs to be allocated at runtime.

We also see optimization potential in the design of the `EventManager` and input processing: both systems could be merged so that input commands are forwarded to interested observers as events according to the principle “Don’t call us, we’ll call you“. It should be noted that appropriate interfaces must be exposed to the game and bottom-up communication must be allowed [7, p. 41]. In addition, a mechanism should derive game-specific `ControlCommands` from input events [33, pp. 21-26].

Within the rendering system, we see a foundation for a modular and extensible render pipeline that currently implements a clear separation between scene description and actual rendering. A key advantage of the chosen design is that individual `RenderPass` instances can be configured with additional options (e.g., *Depth Testing*, *Draw Mode*, *Anti-Aliasing*) and `RenderQueues` can be sorted so that communication with the GPU is as efficient as possible.²⁰ Whether the design proves itself in the implementation of the actual game - and whether all these features are even needed - will become clear as development progresses.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

We have presented *helios*, a prototype game framework developed in C++ for implementing a *Geometry Wars* clone. We discussed the project data and toolchain, introduced the third-party libraries used, and provided an overview of the project’s structure and

¹⁷For a general performance comparison, see [50].

¹⁸These are not limited to component or architectural design; they can reach down to low abstraction levels - “bare metal“ - for example, math-library implementations using SIMD instructions, as provided by `glm` [19]. SIMD - *single instruction, multiple data* - executes a single instruction in parallel on multiple data.

¹⁹See “Refactoring toward Deeper Insight“ [10].

²⁰Unity [48] and OGRE [37] pursue similar concepts; discussions by Christer Ericson [9] address render-pass sorting; Vulkan provides explicit render-pass semantics [25].

architecture.

In the discussion section, we reflected on several challenges encountered during implementation. These reflections raise questions that merit further investigation: How do different forms of the game loop [23, pp. 534-538] affect the game feel? What influence do data structures from the standard library have on runtime when reallocated within the *hot path* of rendering? And what measurable performance gain might result from using *raw pointers* instead of *smart pointers*?

Thanks to the consistent application of well-established development principles, we currently see little need for structural changes. Nevertheless, it would be premature to draw definitive conclusions: Before the technical domain is fully understood, a deeper examination of the intrinsic properties of collision-handling strategies and (artificial) opponent intelligence is still required. We therefore expect several further development iterations in these areas.

In the same context, we remain cautiously optimistic about the design of the rendering pipeline. Its layout follows clear semantic structures and is based on a conceptual idea (*mental model*) of data processing. However, optimal preparation and transfer of rendering instructions to the rendering backend are equally crucial for achieving high performance. Here, our design will have to prove its efficiency in practical application.

Furthermore, our research indicates that DOD²¹-based systems commonly form the foundation of efficient game engines [4]. These systems do not rely solely on classical OOP paradigms but employ data-oriented approaches in performance-critical subsystems, where flat component structures according to the *ECS*²² *pattern* [38] can provide significant performance benefits [55].²³ Although we are not currently pursuing this approach, it remains valuable to consider it as an established paradigm in high-performance game engine design. Future optimizations could incorporate concepts inspired by this methodology.

With all this in mind, it should not be forgotten that we have deliberately prioritized robustness over optimization at this early stage of development. We therefore look forward to subsequent iterations with anticipation. Keeping the project goal of “16 ms per frame“ in view, we conclude this document with a quote by Donald E. Knuth:

“*Premature optimization is the root of all evil.*“ [31]

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²¹*Data-Oriented Design*

²²*Entity-Component System*

²³See also the data-oriented framework *ECS for Unity* [47] in this context. Unreal Engine likewise offers *MassEntity* [15], a “gameplay-focused framework for data-oriented calculations“.

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